

**ANALYSIS OF LEGAL ISSUES IN THE TRADE SECTOR
DURING THE TRANSITION TO A MARKET ECONOMY
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ABSTRACT

The study substantiates that factors such as market imbalances, insufficiently developed regulatory framework, and weak control mechanisms that arose in the context of a transitional economy have influenced the expansion of illegal activities in the trade sector. In particular, speculative transactions, elements of the hidden economy, price manipulation, and exploitation of shortages are analyzed from a scientific perspective. The institutional reforms implemented by the state, the formation of legal regulatory mechanisms, and the evolution of measures to combat violations are also evaluated. The study highlights the theoretical and practical significance of historical experience in ensuring the rule of law in the trade system and forming an effective control system.

First of all, data from the mid- to late 1990s are important in assessing the scale of violations in the trade sector. For example, in archival materials for 1997, 483 trade facilities were inspected, and violations were identified in 164 of them, that is, approximately 33 percent. This indicator means that every third facility in the trade system did not comply with the requirements of the law. Such a high percentage of violations indicates that market relations have not yet been fully formed and the effectiveness of the control system is low. [1, p. 33]

Another important indicator of violations is the volume of illegally sold goods. In 1997, it was recorded that 581.1 thousand soums of goods were illegally sold. This figure was a fairly large amount in the economic conditions of that time and indicates the significant scale of the underground economy in the trade sector. At the same time, this situation negatively affected the reduction of state budget revenues and economic stability. [1, p. 33]

Violations of trade rules were also widely detected during inspections. In particular, 264 violations were recorded as a result of 1,515 raids conducted in 1997. [1, p. 33] This means that on average, a violation was detected in every sixth inspection. These statistics indicate the existence of systemic problems in the trade sector.

Violations in the trade sector were not limited to economic indicators, but also posed a serious threat to public health. For example, during inspections, more than 22 tons of expired food products, as well as alcohol products, were withdrawn from circulation and destroyed.

This situation indicates the weakness of sanitary and quality control in the trade system. If these products had been consumed, this could have led to mass poisoning and other negative consequences.[2]

In addition, problems related to product quality have been noted, including the sale of agricultural products with nitrate levels above the norm. This indicates that there are not only economic, but also environmental and medical risks in the trade sector.

Another violation of the law in the trade sector was the sale of goods without excise stamps and quality certificates. For example, a number of points of sale were found to be selling tobacco and alcoholic beverages without excise taxes. Last year, 40 major criminal cases were initiated on these cases, and since the beginning of 1999, 23 more criminal cases have been opened. These statistics indicate that state bodies have applied criminal liability measures in this area[2].

Another problem in the trade sector is the shortcomings in providing the population with necessary goods. It was found that flour, sugar, soap and pasta were completely absent in 7 of the 27 inspected stores. This means that the basic needs of the population were not met in approximately 26 percent of points of sale. This indicates that there were serious problems in the supply system during the transition to market relations.

In addition, some trade enterprises did not receive the state-allocated commodity funds on time. For example, 796.1 tons of flour, 375 tons of vegetable oil and other products were not received by some organizations in the Samarkand region. This indicates the existence of organizational shortcomings and management problems in the supply system[3].

In the case of the Tashkent region, shortcomings in the trade sector are also evident. Out of 138 trade enterprises inspected in 1994, 98 did not have a full range of mandatory goods. This is 71 percent, which is a very high figure. This indicates a low level of implementation of state policy in the trade system[3].

Among the violations of the law in the trade sector, cases of fraud against the population are also widespread. In particular, cases of underestimating buyers, artificially increasing prices and hiding goods were common. This led to violations of consumer rights. At the same time, certain shortcomings were also observed by state bodies in the trade sector. For example, there were excessive bureaucratic obstacles in the process of issuing licenses and permits to entrepreneurs. This caused dissatisfaction among entrepreneurs and, in some cases, encouraged them to engage in illegal activities.

The state has taken comprehensive measures to combat violations. In particular, 20 complaints were filed by the prosecutor's office, 73 individuals were brought to administrative responsibility, 60 were warned, and 10 criminal cases were initiated. These data indicate a gradual strengthening of state control[4].

Certain results have also been achieved in the field of consumer protection. For example, as a result of inspections, 15 million 287 thousand soums were returned to consumers. This indicates that state bodies have carried out practical work to protect the interests of the population. Fines for violations of the law in the trade sector have also been strengthened. For example, a fine of 25 million soums was applied for cases of failure to issue a check. This indicates that economic responsibility mechanisms are being formed[5].

In general, the statistical data and historical examples presented show that in the early years of independence, the trade sector in Uzbekistan experienced complex and contradictory processes. On the one hand, market relations were formed and the private sector developed, on the other hand, the insufficient legal regulation and control system led to an increase in violations. At the same time, as a result of measures taken by the state, these problems were gradually eliminated and order was established in the trade sector.

Conclusion: In the early years of independence, the trade sector in Uzbekistan was characterized by various violations of the law during the transition to a market economy. Artificially increasing prices, selling low-quality products, and illegal trade practices were widespread. These situations were mainly associated with the weakness of the legal framework and economic difficulties. At the same time, as a result of measures taken by the state, the control system was strengthened and violations of the law were gradually reduced. As a result, legal order and stable market relations were formed in the trade sector.

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